

CHEMICAL ACTIVITY OF HALOGEN DERIVATIVES OF SUBSTITUTED AMIDES OF MALONIC ACID. PART II. VELOCITY OF REPLACEMENT OF CHLORINE ATOM OF THE GROUP $\cdot\text{CHCl}\cdot$ IN MONOCHLORO DERIVATIVES OF SUBSTITUTED AMIDES OF MALONIC ACID

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The following substances have been studied for their chemical activity as expressed by the velocity of replacement of the chlorine atom in them: (1) Monochloromalondiphenylamide. (2) Monochloromalondi-*p*-tolylamide. (3) Monochloromalondi-*o*-tolylamide. (4) Monochloromalondi-1:3:4-xylylamide.

The results indicate that the following factors influence the velocity of replacement of the chlorine atom by hydrogen:

(i) The positions of the radicals like the methyl groups in the nuclear rings attached to the carbonyl groups, (ii) The molecular weights of the residues carried by the carbonyl groups, (iii) The nature of the nuclei attached to the carbonyl groups between which the carbon atom carrying the chlorine atom is situated.

Investigations have been carried out in this laboratory with regard to the stability of chlorine atoms in substances of the following types:—

In this paper, are embodied the observations made with regard to the velocity of the replacement of the chlorine atom in the following substances:—(i) Monochloromalondiphenylamide. (ii) Monochloromalondi-*p*-tolylamide. (iii) Monochloromalondi-*o*-tolylamide. (iv) Monochloromalondi-1:3:4-xylylamide.

The above substances have been prepared as already described in Part I (*vide this Issue*, p. 345) and experiments have been done to study (i) how far the velocity of reduction of the chlorine atom is influenced by the nature of the groups attached to the carbonyl group in the molecule, and (ii) whether the symmetry established in the molecule in the case of a compound such as dichloromalondi-1:3:4-xylylamide has a tendency to bring about stability of the chlorine atoms.

The chlorine has been replaced by hydrogen by treating the chloro derivatives with hydriodic acid.

0.001 Gram mol. of the substance was dissolved in 98% alcohol and the volume was made up to 1 litre. 1 C.c. of this solution was run down from a burette in a conical flask containing a mixture of 2.5 c.c. of *N*/100-potassium iodide solution and 2.5 c.c. of *N*/200-hydrochloric acid solution. Eight such flasks were placed simultaneously at a known time in an electrically regulated thermostat maintained at 30°. At suitable intervals each flask was removed from the thermostat and cooled by adding a piece of ice to the reacting mixture in order to arrest the reaction. The iodine liberated during the reaction was then titrated immediately by means of 0.0004 *N*-sodium thiosulphate solution.

Simultaneously with the above set of experiments an equal number of flasks containing only potassium iodide and hydrochloric acid solution were placed in a thermostat for blank check.

Following is the summary of the results obtained, on studying the velocity of reduction of the chlorine atoms.

Name of the substance.	Time in hours							
	0-15	0-30	0-45	1-00	1-30	2-00	2-33	3-00
	Percentage of chlorine replaced.							
Monochloromalondiphenylamide	9'60	18'40	23'00	25'50	28'80	30'00	30'60	30'90
Monochloromalondi- <i>p</i> -tolylamide	2'60	5'30	8'40	9'70	11'40	12'80	13'60	14'00
Monochloromalondi- <i>o</i> -tolylamide	31'00	30'80	30'60	46'00	52'80	56'80	58'00	59'20
Monochloromalondi-1:3:4-xylylamide	14'20	26'80	35'60	41'70	48'20	52'20	54'80	55'80

In Fig. 1 are drawn the curves for the velocity of the reduction of chlorine in the compounds (i) monochloromalondiphenylamide and (ii) monochloromalondi-1:3:4-xylylamide. As between these two, the higher percentage of reduction in the case of the xylid derivative seems to be the outcome of the high molecular weight of the ring system attached to the carbonyl groups.

The *ortho*-compound shows the highest rate of reduction though the molecular weight of the ring systems in the case of the xylidide derivative is higher; and as such, the latter ought to show the higher rate of reduction than the *ortho*-derivative, as would follow from the above reasoning. The presence of the two methyl groups in the nucleus of the xylidide compound, may mutually influence one another.

From the above considerations, it appears that the following factors govern the velocity of replacement of the chlorine atoms:

(i) The positions of the radicals like the methyl groups in the nuclear rings attached to the carbonyl groups.

(ii) The molecular weight of the residues carried by the carbonyl groups.

(iii) The nature of the nuclei attached to the carbonyl groups between which the carbon atom carrying the chlorine, is situated.

In this connection, reference might be made to the work of Spiers and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 538), who have shown that the valency pulls in a system like: $\begin{matrix} X \\ \diagup \\ C \\ \diagdown \\ X \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} Y \\ \diagup \\ C \\ \diagdown \\ Y \end{matrix}$ will depend not only upon the nature of the radicals but also upon the symmetry established by these in the whole molecule.

For example, in the following systems:

(II), (III), (IV), (V) are unsymmetrical as compared with (I). The tendency, therefore, in the former, will be such that the chlorine atoms in them will be unstable and could be easily replaced. This is actually observed during the investigations carried out in these laboratories. As for example, in the case of (I), where there is a full symmetry around the central carbon atom, it seems that there is a counterbalancing of pulls, and both the chlorine atoms appear to be attached firmly to the central carbon atom, as no chlorine has been found to be reduced under the experimental conditions. This may help us to surmise why the chlorine atom in the unsymmetrical compound *viz.* :—

is reduced, whereas, the corresponding dichloro derivative remains unaffected.

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